

STRUCTURAL THEORY OF RELIABILITY OF LAMINATED REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Probabilistic model of laminated reinforced plastics fracture under flat deterministic or random loading, determined by stages of separate layers failure has been proposed. This model allows to take into account random nature of loading, random properties and a number of layers and geometry of their arranging. Quite simple analytical relationships of prognostication of random strength and reliability of main types of laminates have been obtained on the structural level of layers. Appropriatenesses of strength scale effect depending on material thickness (layers number) and the influence of structural parameters have been shown and analysed.

Keywords: reliability, random strength, laminated plastics, scale effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

For reliability estimation of structures made of laminated reinforced plastics (LRP), it is necessary to have an information about distributions of random properties of materials and random conditions of maintenance [1]. Here, reliability is determined as probability of carrying-out of necessary requests (strength, stiffness, etc.) It is naturally to realize a prognostication of characteristics of LRP random strength on the structural level of layers. Probabilistic models of LRP fracture, based on the conception of "first ply failure", have been considered, for example, in [2-5]. Such models only allow to get lower estimation of reliability. More complex and, accordingly, more adequate models, based on the conception of "multi-step fracture", permit to take into account consecutive stages of single layers failure as far as to the total destruction of material. The Monte Carlo method has got a wide application for analysis of these models [2,5-7, etc.]. Some variants of analytical approaches for probabilistic investigation of LRP strength, taking into account the multi-step process of fracture in principle, have been considered in [8,9]. However, its practical realization is also based on using of computer.

Methods of solution of these probabilistic models use numerical approaches, that calls problems

and complications for its introduction into engineering practice and as well as restricts an inculcation of obtained results in corresponding optimization tasks. Therefore, the purpose of this work is a creation of a simple analytical theory for prognostication of random strength distribution and reliability of LRP under flat loading, taking into account stochastic process of fracture.

2. PROBABILISTIC MODEL

Practically, LRP consist of a large number of layers, arranged in flatness of reinforcement. If a succession of their arranging is determined by periodical law, then structure of their reinforcement may be presented as [...]S. Here, [...] - typical element of structure (TES): for example, as [0/±⊕], [0/90], [±⊕], [0/±⊕/90], etc.; S - a number of such TES. For creation of probabilistic model of fracture, we introduce the following hypothesis: the process of LRP stochastic fracture has a multi-step character, every stage of which is determined by failure of separate TES [10,11].

Thus, the model of LRP comes to a model of parallel joint of uniformity (in statistical meaning) elements. It follows, that the problem of LRP random strength prognostication consists of two successive stages: a) prognostication of random strength of primary element - TES; b) consideration of random strength of "bundle" of such TES. Both these stages may be formulated and solved in analytical form quite simple. Taking into account that flat loading has fundamental significance for LRP in this work we confine to the case of flat stress state.

Note that introduction of offered hypothesis is, in fact, equivalently to the creation of a new level in structural investigations of LRP, hierarchy of which may be presented as: anisotropic homogeneous body → the aggregate of TES → separate layers → components of layers (fibers, polymeric matrix). In the present work we suppose that random properties of layers are known. (Here we indicate σ as layers stresses, $\langle\sigma\rangle$ - TES stresses, $\langle\langle\sigma\rangle\rangle$ - LRP stresses).

3. RANDOM STRENGTH OF TYPICAL ELEMENT OF STRUCTURE

Possibilities of structural prognostication of TES random strength are considered on an example of wide used scheme [0/±⊕], which is in the condition of flat stress state $\langle\sigma_x\rangle$, $\langle\sigma_y\rangle$, $\langle\tau_{xy}\rangle$ (here axis x is parallel to orientation of layer 0°). The deterministic "thread" theory [12] may be used for three-directional reinforced plastics, which are analysed by "multi-step fracture" approach. In this case transversal and shear strength and elastic properties of unidirectional layers are neglected (in comparison with these properties in reinforcement direction) and the model of such TES is a statically determinate system. The condition of safety state is determined by failure of the weakest element (unidirectional layer). Thus reliability of TES $\langle H \rangle$ is written as

$$\langle H \rangle = \prod_{i=1}^3 [1 - P(\sigma_i)], \quad (1)$$

where $P(\sigma)$ - probability of layer failure under stress σ ;

σ_i - stress, arising for layer "i" in direction of reinforcement ($i = 0^\circ; \pm\ominus$) [12];

$$\sigma_0 = [\langle \sigma_x \rangle - \langle \sigma_y \rangle \operatorname{ctg}^2 \Theta] / m; \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{\pm \Theta} = [\langle \sigma_y \rangle / \sin \Theta \mp \langle \tau_{xy} \rangle / \cos \Theta] / [(1-m) \sin \Theta]$$

m - specific thickness of layer with direction 0° .

Let random strength of layers in direction of reinforcement be determined by Weibull's law:

$$P(\sigma) = 1 - \exp[-(\sigma/A)^\beta] \quad (3)$$

and the following relationships be carried out between the components of flat stress state:

$$\langle \sigma_y \rangle / \langle \sigma_x \rangle = k_1; \quad \langle \tau_{xy} \rangle / \langle \sigma_x \rangle = k_2. \quad (4)$$

Consequently, structural expression for estimation of $[0/\pm\Theta]$ TES reliability may be expressed as [13,10]:

$$\langle H \rangle = \exp\{-[\langle \sigma_x \rangle / A']^\beta\}, \quad (5)$$

here

$$A' = A'(m, \Theta, \beta, k_1, k_2) = A \left\{ \left[\frac{1}{m} - \frac{k_1}{m} \operatorname{ctg}^2 \Theta \right]^\beta + \sum_{j=1}^2 \left[\frac{k_1}{(1-m) \sin^2 \Theta} + (-1)^j \frac{k_2}{(1-m) \sin \Theta \cos \Theta} \right]^\beta \right\}^{-\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (6)$$

The value of A' is called a reduced scale parameter [13].

Analogous expressions may be also obtained for other types of TES: it has been elaborated for schemes $[0/\pm\Theta/90]$ and $[0/90]$ in [13], for $[\pm\Theta]$ - in [14]. Note, that "thread" theory has been also used for $[0/\pm\Theta/90]$ and $[0/90]$ TES, but the possibility of layer failure because of transversal normal and shear stresses has been taken into account for scheme $[\pm\Theta]$ [14]. In case of need the necessary expression for estimation of $\langle H \rangle$ may be also obtained for more complex schemes of reinforcement.

4. RELIABILITY OF MULTI-LAYER PLASTICS

The probabilistic model of LRP failure (in accordance with introduced hypothesis) is considered as parallel joint of S uniformity elements, random properties of which are determined by the law (5). Let LRP be under flat stress state $\langle\langle \sigma_x \rangle\rangle$, $\langle\langle \sigma_y \rangle\rangle$, $\langle\langle \tau_{xy} \rangle\rangle$ and relationships similar to (4) take place for them. Thus this model is mathematically equal to a classical task of tension of bundle of threads [15]. However in this case, TES are as "threads" and $\langle\langle \sigma_x \rangle\rangle$ is as tension stress (components $\langle\langle \sigma_y \rangle\rangle$, $\langle\langle \tau_{xy} \rangle\rangle$ are taken into account through coefficients k_1 , k_2 in the value of

A'). Neglecting the contribution of destroyed TES and in accordance with [16] we have for reliability of LRP $\langle\langle H_S \rangle\rangle$:

$$\langle\langle H_S \rangle\rangle = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^S (-1)^{i+1} \binom{S}{i} \{1 - \langle P[\langle\langle \sigma_X \rangle\rangle] \rangle\}^i \quad (7)$$

$$\{1 - \langle\langle H_{S-i}[\langle\langle \sigma_{X_i} \rangle\rangle] \rangle\},$$

where

$$\langle\langle \sigma_{X_i} \rangle\rangle = \langle\langle \sigma_X \rangle\rangle S / (S-i) ;$$

$$\langle\langle H_0 \rangle\rangle = 0; \quad \langle P \rangle = 1 - \langle H \rangle$$

Taking into account that the distribution of $\langle\langle H_S \rangle\rangle$ develops to the normal law with increasing of S [15], the main statistical characteristics are of practical interest. Figure 1 shows the dependence of mean value $\langle\langle \sigma_X \rangle\rangle$ and coefficient of variation v_{σ_X} of LRP strength on TES number and degree of dispersedness of TES strength properties (β). From Fig.1 it can be seen the presence of scale effect connected with material thickness: mean value and degree of dispersedness (v_{σ_X}) of LRP strength is reduced with increasing of S . This tendency is expressed more brightly with greater dispersedness of layers strength properties and with $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ (deterministic solution) the scale effect is absent. Experimental corroboration of scale effect of LRP strength has been shown on the example of axial tension of multi-layered unidirectional graphite/epoxy plastics [17].

Figure 1. Dependence of mean value $\langle\langle \sigma_X \rangle\rangle$ and coefficient of variation v_{σ_X} of laminate strength on S and β .

Obtained results may be also used in case of random loading. Let random components $\langle\langle\sigma_i\rangle\rangle$ ($i=x,y,xy$) be determined by probability density functions $P_{\sigma_i}(\sigma)$. Then in accordance with [1] reliability of LRP is determined as (with satisfied exactness for practical applications):

$$\langle\langle H_s \rangle\rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P_{\sigma_x}(\sigma) \langle\langle H_s(\sigma) \rangle\rangle d\sigma. \quad (8)$$

More exact analytical methods of $\langle\langle H_s \rangle\rangle$ calculation, taking into account the difference between the degree of dispersedness of $\langle\langle\sigma_i\rangle\rangle$ and its possible correlation, have been elaborated in [18].

5. CONCLUSION

Proposed apportionment of a new additional structural level in stochastic investigation of LRP strength leads to quite simple method of reliability prognostication. It may be used both under deterministic and under random flat loading. Obtained results may be used for the solution of the following practically important back problems: setting of "safety conditions"; optimization of LRP structure by the criterion of reliability maximum; indirect estimation of layers random strength properties on the basis of experimental investigations of LRP; etc. Such approach may be very perspective not only for analysis of flat loading, but as well as for structural investigation of bending strength of multi-layer composites.

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